

Agenda for Future Research

Inclusive and Sustainable Mobility

The ACCTING project explores the impact of Green Deal policies on individual and collective behaviours, provides evidence, and empowers policymakers and stakeholders to anticipate and mitigate potential negative effects.

Its Agenda for Future Research highlights key research gaps across Green Deal policy areas and provides a clear overview of research priorities and needs for a fair and sustainable transition. By doing so, it aims to contribute to the development of future research agendas and pave the way for inclusive and effective policymaking and implementation.

The full set of research agendas covering other thematic areas can be found [on the ACCTING project website](#).

Despite a substantial body of research illustrating how car dependency and transport policies disproportionately impact marginalised groups, the uptake of intersectional and gender-responsive approaches by policymakers remains limited. Many case studies detail successful inclusive and sustainable mobility initiatives, yet these examples are not consistently translated into policy. Key questions arise: What prevents policymakers and other privileged actors from integrating the knowledge and frameworks that already exist? How do political will, administrative structures, and broader socio-cultural norms influence whether and how equitable, sustainable measures are adopted?

Moreover, research on user behaviour often examines the experiences of marginalised communities, particularly in the context of transport poverty, exploring how they respond to or are affected by transport policies. While this type of research is crucial, future studies must also delve into policymaker behaviour and the structural or systemic barriers that inhibit equitable policy design, implementation, and enforcement. Understanding the motivations, resistances, and capacities of policymakers (and other influential stakeholders) will help bridge the gap between evidence-based recommendations and real-world policy outcomes.

ACCTING Findings

Car Dependency and Resistance to Change

Car dependency results from the interdependent relationships of social, cultural, political, historical, geographical and technical systems. This includes both structural (such as urban planning and infrastructure that prioritise car use), social and cultural (that frame cars as symbols of freedom, masculinity, and a “good life,” often leading to resistance when restrictions on car use are proposed) and policy and political factors (that may fail to provide viable alternatives, limiting policymakers’ willingness or ability to impose restrictions on private car use).

Policies aimed at reducing car use can face public or political resistance if alternatives (e.g., accessible public transport) are insufficiently funded or poorly designed. The lack of affordable and convenient transportation alternatives discourages people from reducing car use. Moreover, transport choices are shaped not only by the availability of accessible options but also by constraints in transport infrastructure that support active mobility, such as walking and cycling, as well as socioeconomic limitations and living conditions.

Disproportionate Impact on Marginalised Groups

Marginalised populations, including low-income individuals, elderly people, and disabled persons, disproportionately bear the burden of car-free policies due to limited resources to adapt. For example, low-emission zones force economically disadvantaged groups to upgrade their vehicles where few or no sustainable alternatives exist, a cost they cannot always afford.

However, policy-level failures, for instance, not incorporating equity-focused measures or ignoring intersectional vulnerabilities, can exacerbate negative impacts. Even when gender+ and intersectional research provides robust evidence, these insights do not always translate into inclusive policy design.

Public transport systems in many regions do not adequately address the mobility needs of disadvantaged populations. Women are more dependent on public transport and other non-car modes than men due to a number of factors, including unbalanced economic conditions (still more men than women own and have access to private cars), the strong connection between men, masculinity and cars, time-spatial organisation of work and everyday life. Men show stronger resistance to car-free policies because of cultural associations between cars and autonomy or status have tended to favour those transport patterns associated with men and masculinity and less so those associated with women's needs and their disproportionated care responsibilities.

Patterns of Public Response and Policy Design

Policies are often perceived as being implemented in a top-down manner, with limited community engagement or consultation. Disadvantaged groups feel, and often are, particularly excluded from decision-making processes, even when they are most affected by sustainable transport policies. In some cases, their marginal position also limits the extent to which they are affected by these policies (for example, if they do not own a car). Distrust is heightened by perceptions of hidden agendas, such as prioritising revenue generation over public well-being. Privileged groups, on the other hand, can mount stronger resistance (e.g., lobbying against car-free zones) or simply circumvent restrictions (e.g., by purchasing electric vehicles). From a policy-learning perspective, the tension lies in developing strategies that encourage genuine engagement and address community-specific needs without simply yielding to the most vocal or financially influential groups.

Citizens' responses to car-free policies can vary widely, ranging from positive adaptation to active resistance. Disadvantaged groups may find it more difficult to take an active stance, for example due to resource constraints or the presence of other more pressing priorities, while groups that are relatively less exposed to social and economic hardship tend to be more vocal in their opposition, especially when policies restrict car use without providing viable alternatives for them. It is not uncommon for affluent people to escape car-free measures by adopting individual solutions (e.g. by buying electric cars that also allow access to low emission zones or paying for expensive parking or congestion charges). Although one goal of these measures is to reduce or replace petrol vehicles with cleaner alternatives, such actions limit the benefits aimed from these policies such as congestion or noise reduction. Gender also matters. For example, women are more likely than men to support car-free policies, be concerned about environmental issues, adopt or maintain sustainable mobility behaviour, and be open to sustainable mobility in general.

Policies with visible infrastructural benefits, such as improved public transport or the installation of bike lanes, gain better public reception than purely regulatory measures like low-emission zones, also because people perceive the latter as more reversible and easier to change than the former. Successful initiatives emphasise participatory processes that address equity, accessibility, and community-specific needs while delivering immediate benefits like reduced congestion and better transport services. This fosters trust and long-term behavioural change.

Cycling as a Tool for Inclusive Mobility

Cycling initiatives are integral to achieving an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal by promoting access, competence, and embrace at personal, societal, and systemic levels. By promoting cycling and lowering barriers for cycling, cycling promotion initiatives contribute to reducing greenhouse gas emissions, noise, and congestion while fostering active lifestyles.

However, marginalised groups face barriers such as costs, inadequate infrastructure, and lack of cycling skills. Gender, socioeconomic status, disabilities and ethnicity intersect to exacerbate these challenges, with cultural norms and societal expectations creating additional hurdles, especially for women with migrant backgrounds. While all cyclists are vulnerable in cities primarily designed for cars, some cyclists experience greater challenges within car-dominated transport systems, namely those who are both vulnerable and reliant on additional support (i.e., children, seniors, and disabled people).

Despite the potential for community-building and independence, broader societal barriers like unsafe traffic conditions limit cycling's long-term adoption. Gender-sensitive and separatist approaches (e.g., women-only bike schools) effectively address specific cultural and gendered barriers.

Behavioural and Systemic Impacts of Mobility Policies

Participants in targeted mobility initiatives, such as bike schools, report increased confidence, competence, and independence. Social aspects, such as breaking social isolation and building community are other impacts of importance along with mobility skills taught, that lowered barriers for cycling.

Scaling these initiatives to meet European Green Deal goals remains challenging due to inconsistent regional support and infrastructure. Recommendations highlight the importance of participatory policy design, targeted investments, and addressing systemic barriers to ensure equity and sustainability. Understanding policymaker motivations, organisational structures, and potential barriers is key to embedding these initiatives within broader mobility strategies.

Research gaps and directions for future research

Subtheme 1. Sustainability and Behavioural Transformation

In the context of transport poverty, much of the existing studies often examines the experiences and behaviour of marginalised communities, while overlooking policy-level actors and their role in shaping sustainable transport measures. There is also an insufficient understanding of how and why policy changes occur in some contexts but not in others, despite extensive evidence on the importance of gender+ and intersectionality.

Research questions

Policymaker and Institutional Behaviour:

- What institutional, political, and cultural factors enable policymakers to propose, sustain, or scale up car-free and other sustainable transport policies in some contexts but not in others?
- What can be learned from successful policy change in terms of replicating or adapting effective interventions elsewhere?

Policy-Level Change for Collective Practices

- Which regulatory frameworks and policy tools can effectively encourage collective mobility practices while maintaining fairness, preventing unintended consequences, and ensuring that disadvantaged groups are not marginalised, thereby fostering inclusive benefits for all citizens?

Gendered Perceptions and Cultural Dynamics

- To what extent are gendered and cultural perceptions (e.g., cars as symbols of masculinity, trip-chaining requirements for women) shifting, and what targeted policy interventions can effectively address these shifting perceptions?
- What are the main sources of resistance (both within policymaking circles and among the public) to implementing policies that address gendered mobility needs, and how do these differ across cultural contexts?

Unintended and Indirect Effects

- What unintended consequences (both positive and negative) arise when implementing car-free or low-car policies (e.g., reinforcing inequalities, fostering new forms of civic engagement), and how can policymakers anticipate and mitigate them?
- How do policy approaches (including consultation processes, funding mechanisms, and partnerships with civil society) shape these outcomes?

Subtheme 2. Intersectionality in Mobility Transition

Although a wealth of research examines how overlapping vulnerabilities (e.g., socioeconomic, gender, ethnicity) shape mobility experiences, policymaking processes often do not systematically integrate intersectional findings into transport policies. Recent work shows that intersectionality is increasingly acknowledged in theory. However, questions remain about how to encourage more consistent application of these insights in practice. Identifying the institutional, cultural, and political factors that shape the uptake of intersectional approaches can inform strategies to close the gap between research and policy implementation.

Research questions

Institutional Factors and Knowledge Utilisation

- What institutional, administrative, or cultural dynamics make it challenging for policymakers to consistently apply intersectional research when designing and implementing mobility policies?
- How can co-designed intervention studies—involving both researchers and policymakers—test and refine practical methods for translating intersectional insights into actionable policies?

Challenges in Implementation and Pathways to Change

- Which challenges (e.g., political priorities, resource limitations, stakeholder alignment) commonly arise when introducing intersectional mobility policies, and how can they be addressed or mitigated?
- To what extent can corporate and industry actors—through corporate social responsibility or public-private partnerships—support the development and uptake of equity-focused mobility solutions?
- How can cooperative planning and participatory processes (with vulnerable groups, NGOs, local communities) strengthen policy relevance, ensuring that policies align more closely with on-the-ground realities?

Gender+ Inclusion

- Does increased gender+ diversity among policymakers (transport officials, urban planners, street-level bureaucrats) correlate with more inclusive policy measures and stronger utilisation of intersectional frameworks?
- Which institutional mechanisms—such as diversity mandates, targeted hiring, or enhanced public consultation—have the greatest potential to foster inclusive policymaking processes?
- How can a more diverse policy environment facilitate better engagement with marginalised communities, supporting co-creation and more equitable outcomes?

Digital Access and the Adoption of Sustainable Mobility Solutions

- How do digital access and literacy (or lack thereof) affect the ability of marginalised groups to adopt app-based public transport systems, bike-sharing platforms, and other technology-driven mobility innovations?
- Which policy interventions or community-based programmes most effectively bridge digital divides, ensuring that new mobility solutions are equitable and accessible to all?

Subtheme 3. Participatory Policy Design and Urban Planning

Although there is a good number of studies on co-design processes that involve both citizens and policymakers, much of the existing research relies on single-case or small-N comparative approaches. This creates a gap in understanding how co-design is planned, implemented, and evaluated across diverse political and cultural settings, and which factors promote or hinder larger-scale adoption of participatory policymaking. A systematic, large-N comparative perspective could yield valuable insights into how local authorities navigate resource constraints, political pressures, and cultural differences to adopt or avoid co-design approaches in urban transport planning.

Research questions

Large-N Comparative Studies and Cross-Cultural Variations

- How can larger-N or cross-national comparative analyses reveal patterns of success or failure in participatory approaches, especially in terms of equity and sustainability outcomes?
- In what ways do political structures (e.g., centralised vs. decentralised governance), cultural norms, and administrative capacities shape the effectiveness of co-design in different regional contexts?
- How might best practices be scaled up or adapted to ensure participatory policy design remains responsive to varied local realities?

Local Policy-Making Perspective: Enablers and Barriers

- What institutional, administrative, and political factors at the local level influence whether co-design processes are initiated or sustained in urban transport planning?
- How do local policymakers weigh potential benefits (e.g., broader support, improved legitimacy) against perceived risks (e.g., increased complexity, potential conflict) when deciding whether to adopt co-design methods?

Mitigating Environmental-Social Tensions and Protest Dynamics

- How can co-design processes help moderate tensions between social and environmental priorities, including resistance from groups that may be torn between different values (e.g., social justice vs. strict environmental measures)?
- Under what conditions do protest movements aligned with or against sustainable mobility measures gain or lose momentum, and how can participatory policy design address grievances (specific worries, fears, or disagreements people have about mobility policies) to foster more inclusive outcomes?

Subtheme 4. Environmental and Public Health Impacts

Extensive research demonstrates that reducing car dependency in urban environments can improve physical, mental, and social well-being. Walking and cycling, for instance, have been linked to lower rates of obesity, cardiovascular disease, and diabetes, as well as reduced symptoms of anxiety and depression. Beyond individual health, improved air quality and reduced noise pollution in areas with fewer cars contribute to better respiratory health, healthier sleep patterns, and greater social cohesion.

Despite these well-documented benefits, not all population groups experience them equally. Low-income and marginalised communities often have limited access to safe, convenient active transport infrastructure, while women and older adults may face additional barriers related to safety, cultural norms, or mobility constraints. Consequently, the challenge is not just proving that reduced car use has positive health outcomes—this is widely acknowledged—but ensuring equitable access to those benefits across diverse demographics and different urban contexts. Questions remain about the most effective policy interventions, how these interventions vary by context, and how to equitably distribute the resulting health benefits.

Research questions

Comparative Effectiveness of Interventions

- Which policy measures (e.g., dedicated bike lanes, congestion charges, car-free zones) most effectively promote physical, mental, and social health, and how do these effects differ across contexts and population groups?

Equitable Distribution of Health Benefits

- How different types of transport interventions (e.g., congestion pricing, low-emission zones, improved cycling infrastructure) influence health outcomes for specific demographic groups?
- Which contextual factors (e.g. local governance structures, cultural norms, or existing inequalities) affect the success and replicability of these interventions?

About ACCTING

ACCTING is an EU-funded project aiming to understand the impact of Green Deal policies on vulnerable groups, prevent inequalities, and produce knowledge and innovations to advance behavioural change at individual and collective levels.

As the project approaches its conclusion in May 2025, the research team has developed a Research Agenda outlining key knowledge gaps across Green Deal policy areas. This document serves as a valuable reference for future research and policymaking.

Discover the [Research Agenda published during the first research cycle](#).

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